

Spin-Orbit Photonics in 3D Rotated Anisotropic Materials

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Abstract: We investigate light propagation in point-wise rotated anisotropic materials, where rotations are non-planar. We demonstrate the emergence of effective electric and magnetic fields –proportional to the gradient of the rotation angle- acting on the photons.
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1. Introduction

Spin-orbit photonics (SOP) refers to optical systems where the light polarization strongly affects the intensity profile [1, 2]. Although this is an intrinsic property of the Maxwell's equations (see for example the spatial walk-off in anisotropic materials or the longitudinal field for tightly polarized beams in vacuum), only in the last few years the field attracted a great deal of attention, partially due to the introduction of structured materials (e.g., metamaterials) in the optical domain. One of the most representative phenomena in SOP is the wavefront modulation via the Pancharatnam-Berry phase (PBP), a particular type of geometric phase: in an anisotropic material subject to a point-wise rotation in the plane normal to the wavevector, a phase delay is imparted on the wavefront proportional to two times the local rotation angles [3]. This property enables the realization of a new class of photonic devices featuring a polarization-dependent response, the latter well suited to be engineered [4]. On the other hand, when the optical axis is rotated on the plane containing the wavevector, a change in the extraordinary refractive index occurs [5]. Thus, in this case only gradients in the dynamic phase are affecting how light propagates inside the sample. Here we will focus on the regime where the two rotations occur together, demonstrating how light in this configuration behaves like a charged particle subjected to an effective electromagnetic field determined by the spatial distribution of the rotation.

2. Modelling of light propagation in a 3D rotated material

Under the paraxial approximation, an optical beam with vacuum wavenumber $k_0 = 2\pi/\lambda$ propagating along z in an uniaxial medium of birefringence Δn and average refractive index \bar{n} is influenced only by the values of the dielectric tensor involving components on the transverse plane xy , i.e., the optical field can be modelled like a two component field, analogously to a spin 1/2 elemental particle. The direction of the optical axis is determined by the azimuthal angle $\phi(\mathbf{r})$ -supposed to be in the form $\phi = \Gamma(x, y) \sin(2\pi z/\Lambda)$ ($\Lambda = \lambda/\Delta n$ is the polarization beat length) in agreement with the experiments shown below- and the zenith angle $\theta(\mathbf{r})$. Exploiting the analogy with a Pauli equation, light in propagation perceives an effective electric potential U_{eff} and magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{eff} given by

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}} = k_0 \left(n_e^{(0)} - n_{\perp} \right) \Gamma(x, y) \hat{y} + \frac{k_0}{4\bar{n}} V_{\text{dyn}}(x, y) \hat{z}, \quad (1)$$

$$U_{\text{eff}} = -\frac{1}{4k_0\bar{n}} \left[(\nabla_{xy}\Gamma)^2 + \left(\frac{2\pi}{\Lambda} \right)^2 \Gamma^2 \right] + \frac{k_0}{4\bar{n}} V_{\text{dyn}}(x, y), \quad (2)$$

where $V_{\text{dyn}} = n_e^2 - \bar{n}^2$, $n_e(\theta)$ being the extraordinary refractive index. The terms V_{dyn} provides the gradient with respect to the variations in the refractive index of the extraordinary component. Roughly speaking, \mathbf{B}_{eff} yields changes in the geometric phase, whereas gradients of V_{dyn} are related with a modulation of the dynamic phase. According to Eqs. (1-2), in the general case both geometric and dynamic phase are acting together: indeed, the ordinary and the extraordinary component cannot be separated, that means, the polarization of any field will evolve along z , thus inducing a PBP transverse gradient. Owing to the presence of two components in \mathbf{B}_{eff} , the quasi-modes will be featuring a spatially-varying polarization across the transverse plane, the latter being determined by the local values of θ and ϕ .

3. Experiments in nematic liquid crystals

The theoretical ideas discussed above were tested with respect to nonlinear effects in nematic liquid crystals (NLCs). Indeed, the 3D structuring required to observe the effects described above is quite demanding from a technological point of view. In NLCs the optical axis is rotated by applying an electric field, an effect called reorientational nonlinearity at optical frequencies [5]. As a matter of fact, external electric fields induce a dipole in the molecules, which in turn try to re-align with the external stimulus. In our experiments, the optical axis at rest is parallel to the propagation direction z . We then use the voltage, applied along the y direction, to rotate the molecules on the plane containing both the optical axis and the wavevector, yz . The voltage-induced rotation tunes the relative weight of dynamic and geometric phase in determining the light propagation. For large enough powers, the molecular direction is also changed by the optical beam. According to the light polarization, the optical beam will induce nonlinearly a phase gradient, ranging from purely dynamic (polarization along y , regardless of the applied bias) to pure geometric in nature (voltages large enough to completely align the optical axis to the direction of the low-frequency electric field) [6]. Such a nonlinear gradient, regardless of its origin, induces self-localization, see Fig. 1(a). The different dependence of the self-trapping on the input polarization and applied bias allows us to identify the different regimes for the light propagation: pure dynamic at 3 V, pure geometric at 10 V, and an intermediate power-dependent interplay at 5 V, see Fig. 1. The strong dependence on the input polarization shown in Fig. 1(b) proves the nonlinear spin-orbit interaction and its tunability with the applied bias.

Fig. 1. Measured average (versus z) beam width for (a) input circular polarizations versus the input power and (b) for a rotating linear polarization versus the polarization direction for a fixed input power. In both the panels the curves are parameterized with respect to the applied bias (peak value).

In conclusion, we theoretically and numerically showed how optical beam propagation in 3D rotated anisotropic materials can be modelled with a Pauli equation, leading to a plethora of structured beams with controllable characteristics. Experimentally, using the optically-induced rotation of the optical axis we demonstrated a whole class of self-trapped beams existing thanks to interplay between geometric and dynamic phase.

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